

EFFECT OF NATURAL AGEING ON ELECTRICAL CONDUCTIVITY (dSm⁻¹) OF SOYBEAN

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Abstract

The present investigation was conducted at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani, and the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli, using soybean varieties MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162. Natural ageing was studied by storing seeds under conventional (uncontrolled) storage conditions and evaluating them at intervals of 0, 60, 120, 180, and 240 days for seed quality and biochemical parameters. Observations on different seed quality traits, such as germination percentage, were recorded at regular intervals. The soybean variety MAUS-162 was found to perform better in terms of biochemical parameters, including malondialdehyde, superoxide dismutase, peroxide activity, protein, oil, and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, natural ageing, temperature

Introduction

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop belonging to the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean plays a crucial role in agriculture and export, especially in times of energy crises and shortages. It has now become a significant oil and seed crop, offering a cost-effective alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are rich in protein, carbohydrates, and fats, and are an excellent source of vitamins, minerals, and beneficial plant compounds such as isoflavones. With its high nutritional value, soybean has great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food.

Soybean seeds reach their maximum potential for germination and vigor at physiological maturity. However, the germination (viability) of soybean seeds is relatively short compared to other oil crops and often declines before sowing. This loss of germination is more severe in tropical conditions, like those in India. The environmental conditions in these regions make it challenging to maintain seed viability during storage. One of the key factors contributing to this challenge is the various biochemical changes that occur in soybeans during storage. Generally, more vigorous seeds can withstand high temperatures and humidity while still producing normal seedlings.

Field performance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which is negatively impacted by different aging periods and storage conditions. As soybean seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture, which leads to various biochemical changes in the seeds during storage.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out with the aim of assessing the seed viability of plant species with high oil content and their germination after being stored and aged for a certain period. Based on the assessment of aged seed vigor, we can determine its field emergence capacity and the potential for forming vigorous, healthy plants that will be high-yielding.

The experimental material for the investigation consisted of four soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill) varieties, representing two maturity groups: MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (early maturity group: 93-95 days),

Table 1: Effect of natural ageing on Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean varieties

	0 DAH	60 DAH	120 DAH	180 DAH	240 DAH	Mean V
MAUS 71	0.52	0.78	0.98	1.80	1.99	1.21
MAUS 158	0.50	0.75	1.00	1.70	1.96	1.18
JS-335	0.55	0.78	1.02	1.80	2.01	1.23
MAUS 162	0.42	0.68	0.91	1.50	1.88	1.08
Mean D	0.50	0.75	0.98	1.70	1.96	

TABLE OF SEM, SED AND C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	0.06	0.03	0.02
Factor(D)	0.07	0.03	0.02
Factor(V X D)	N/A	0.06	0.05

and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (late maturity group: 95-103 days) (Loeffler et al., 1988). The seed material was evaluated for different seed quality parameters, such as seed moisture, under natural aging conditions. Seed quality parameters were assessed at 0, 60, 120, 180, and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion

The data on the effect of varieties and storage days on Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean seed during natural ageing are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1.

It is clear that there was a significant effect of genotype on the Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean seed (Table 1). Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) increased after natural ageing in all four varieties (Table 1). The lowest Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) was observed in the variety MAUS-162 (0.42 dSm⁻¹), which was significantly lower than in MAUS-158 (0.50 dSm⁻¹), MAUS-71 (0.52 dSm⁻¹), and JS-335 (0.55 dSm⁻¹) at the initial stage of the study.

The Electrical Conductivity of seed leachates increased significantly in all four varieties as the storage period progressed. The increase was slow up to 120 days of storage, but after that, it accelerated. At the end of the storage period, JS-335 (2.00 dSm⁻¹) recorded the maximum seed leachates, followed by MAUS-71 (1.99 dSm⁻¹), MAUS-158 (1.96 dSm⁻¹), and MAUS-162 (1.88 dSm⁻¹).

Panobianco and Vieira (1996) reported that different genotypes could be significantly affected by Electrical Conductivity. Conductivity increases with the length of storage time. Shah and Wahida Sultan (2008) also showed that seepage conductance increases with seed age in soybean varieties. Similar results were reported by Agrawal and Siddiqui (1973). In this regard, KarLing (1978) noted that the increase in Electrical Conductivity could be due to an increase in membrane permeability, which damages the seed during storage.

Panobianco and Vieira (1996) further reported that Electrical Conductivity varied among soybean varieties, attributing this variation to the lignin content of the seed coat. High lignin content is considered a desirable property to improve soybean quality. Similar findings were reported by Halder and Gupta (1980), Pallavi et al. (2003) in sunflower seeds, Narwal (1995) in okra, and Verma et al. (2003) in *Brassica spp.*

Note V = Variety D= Day's after Harvesting

Fig. 1: Effect of natural ageing on Electrical Conductivity (dSm⁻¹) of soybean varieties

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